

THE ROLE OF OUTDOOR GAMES IN ATHLETICS

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of improving the technical readiness of students in athletics through the use of outdoor games.

Key words: health, athletics, exercise technique, teaching methods, outdoor games.

Introduction: In the field of physical education in recent years, there has been an intensive search, the development of new technologies that can provide a personal approach to each student, to the problem of his health and his level of preparedness [1].

Improving the methods, forms and means of teaching is becoming one of the necessary conditions for the effective development and functioning of modern higher education [2].

The development of conditions for the formation of motivation and increasing the need for health promotion of students, the definition of methods and means of improving the health of students is an important task in the work of physical education departments [3, 4].

According to the results of the annual survey, most first-year students do not go in for physical culture and sports regularly [5]. The number of students who, for health reasons, need classes in a special medical group, increases from year to year, and is approximately 30%. And students who are engaged in the main group cannot always successfully pass the control standards and fully perform physical activity in accordance with the program of physical education. In the process of forming a person's individuality, physical education plays a special role. It contributes to the formation of a healthy lifestyle [6, 7].

Athletics has always been the basis of school and university programs in the subject "Physical Education" [8, 9]. But quite often, classes are reduced only to the adoption of standards for running and jumping. No attention is paid to mastering the technique of athletics exercises. Such an attitude to the conduct of classes discourages the desire of students to engage in physical education.

No one wants to appear ridiculous and awkward in the eyes of others while engaging in various types of physical activity. Formation of internal motivation for physical culture takes place in parallel with mastering the technique of exercises, when satisfaction comes from their correct performance [10, 11]. The higher the technical skill of a person, the more confident he feels on the treadmill or in the jump sector, on the playground.

Athletics is the most popular sport and occupies a leading position in the system of physical education due to its diversity, accessibility, applied value [12, 13, 14]. Athletics is based on physical exercises that are natural for every person: movements that each of us masters from childhood. These are walking, running, jumping and throwing. Mastering their basics begins for the child with the first independent steps [15]. Later, in a variety of games with peers, the guys, without thinking about it, improve these skills. For many, it is with such games that acquaintance with sports begins [16].

But, the older the children become, the less often outdoor games are used as a teaching method and a means of developing motor skills. A well-known theorist in the field of physical culture Z. Gilevich gives the following definition: "a game is one of the forms of human activity, voluntarily performed individually or in a group, in which obtaining the final result does not play a significant role, but emotional perception, feelings, a sense of freedom of action and imagination make it look completely different from work."

In the physical education of students of pedagogical universities, outdoor games perform the following functions:

- an important means of recovery, development of physical qualities;
- a means of revitalization and diversity of activities, outdoor activities;
- a means of eliminating emotional and physical tension;
- a means of professionally applied physical training [17, 18].

Mastering motor skills, fine coordination of movements is faster if it is not associated with the need to apply great muscle strength or endurance. Therefore, when teaching the correct technique, it is necessary to use a large number of various outdoor games with elements of athletics [19, 20]. Moreover, it is important to teach many and varied movements. Exercises in games also contribute to the development of physical qualities: speed, endurance, strength, flexibility and dexterity. The effect in the development of motor skills and qualities, in turn, will lead to improved results in the performance of various tests.

Correctly and qualitatively carried out preparation for the main part of the classes makes it possible to attract additional volume of blood to the muscles, which is in the reserve at rest. A warm-up leads to the expansion of blood vessels, the preparation of the respiratory system, and a reduction in the time of the motor reaction. Thus, the warm-up increases the efficiency of the body, contributes to the psychological mood for further training. Running is ideal for athletics. But it is often very boring for students of non-physical education specialties to "wind" circles around the stadium.

The use of outdoor games in the classroom with students of the Pedagogical Institute allows not only to develop their physical qualities and tactical skills, but also, within the framework of the program for professionally applied physical training, to form organizational skills in them, to teach methodological techniques for conducting outdoor games. The game is an important tool in the work of a teacher. It will help to determine the character and temperament of each student. In skillful hands, the game will help in team building, organizing students at breaks and extracurricular activities.

Conclusions. From the above, we can conclude that the game is multifunctional in nature. It helps in implementing the principles of a healthy lifestyle, achieving a high level of health and capacity for students. The game has an effective impact on the physical and mental development of the individual, is an invaluable assistant in pedagogical activity. Everyone loves to play. And the older the students, the more they enjoy playing.

References:

1. Alikulovich M. K. (2022). Methodology for Carrying out Swimming Training Lessons for Children 9-10 Years Old. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 36-38.
2. Alikulovich M. K., & Yuldashevich T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(3).
3. Alikulovich M. K. (2022). Mobile Games on the Water as a Means of Developing the Physical Qualities of School Children. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 783–786.
4. Менгликулов, Х. (2022). 14-15 ёшдаги сузувчиларда тезлик-куч сифатларини ривожлантириш услубиёти. *Жамият ва инновациялар*, 3(6/S), 81–87.
5. Menglikulov, Khairulla (2021). “Features of organization of general physical preparation in lesson and extracurricular activities”, *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*: Vol. 2021: Iss. 2, Article 6.
6. Менгликулов, Х. А. (2020). Особенности физической подготовки специалистов физической культуры в высшем учебном заведении. *Педагогика ва психологияда инновациялар*, 11(3).
7. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022). Method of developing speed-strength qualities in young swimmers 12-14 years. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 179-182.

8. Abdullaev Y. (2021). Forms and methods of developing the use of folk movement games in high school students. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(2), 73-79.
9. Abdullaev Yashnarzhon Makhkamovich. (2021). Physical education of senior schools by means of folk moving games. *European Scholar Journal*, 2(11), 70-72.
10. Абдуллаев Я. М., Турдимуродов Д. Й. Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов / Я. М. Абдуллаев, Д. Ю. Турдимуродов // *Colloquium-journal*. - 2020. -№ 24-2(76). -С. 14-16.
11. Абдуллаев Я. М., & Турдимуродов Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
12. Makhkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Mobile games for school children. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 202–205.
13. Makhkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Innovative Approaches to the Formation of the Voluntary Qualities of Students-Athletes. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 17–20.
14. Abdullaev, Y. M., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Creation of pedagogical conditions in the formation of volitional grades in primary school students. *Colloquium-journal*.
15. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. *Problems and scientific solutions, Australia, Melbourne*.
16. Turdimurodov, D. (2022). Volitional qualities of a person and their formation in adolescent age. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(14), 13-17.
17. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2022, September). Formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. In *International scientific conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 198-204).

18. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education*, 3(7), 283-289.
19. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.
20. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current research journal of pedagogics*, 2(09), 47-51.